

Exploration of Topological Indices on Chemical Compounds

A Report

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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This is to certify that entitled “**Exploration of Topological Indices on Chemical Compounds**” submitted by **Dr. USHA A** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafede record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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Synopsis

In recent years, graph theory has established itself as an important mathematical tool in a wide variety of subjects, ranging from operational research and chemistry to genetics and linguistics, and from electrical engineering and geography to sociology and architecture. At the same time, it has also emerged as a worthwhile mathematical discipline. Graphs serve as mathematical models to analyze many concrete real-world problems successfully. Certain problems in physics, chemistry, communication science, computer technology, genetics, psychology, sociology, and linguistics can be formulated as problems in graph theory. Also, many branches of mathematics, such as group theory, matrix theory, probability, and topology, have close connections with graph theory. Some puzzles and several problems of a practical nature have been instrumental in the development of various topics in graph theory. The famous Königsberg "bridge problem" has been the inspiration for the development of Eulerian graph theory. Leonard Euler in 1735 introduced the concept of graphs to the citizens of Prussia when they posed a puzzle to mathematicians. It was a famous Königsberg Bridge problem that helped Graph theory to evolve. This puzzle was just a starting and in no time Graph theory became famous and found its applications in many areas of science.

The challenging Hamiltonian graph theory has been developed from the "Around the World" game of Sir William Hamilton. The theory of acyclic graphs was developed for solving problems of electrical networks, and the study of "trees" was developed for enumerating isomers of organic compounds. The well-known four-color problem formed the very basis for the development of planarity in graph theory and combinatorial topology. Problems of linear programming and operations research (such as maritime traffic problems) can be tackled by the theory of flows in networks. Kirkman's schoolgirl problem and scheduling problems are examples of problems that can be solved by graph colorings. The study of simplicial complexes can be associated with the study of graph theory. Many more such problems can be added to this list.

Graph theory being a branch of Mathematics deals with networks spreading its applications in almost every field. It has widened its applications in chemistry, biology, computer science, engineering and many more areas.

A single number, representing a chemical structure in graph-theoretical terms via the molecular graph, is called a topological descriptor and if it in addition correlates with a molecular property it is called topological index, which is used to understand physicochemical properties of chemical compounds. Topological indices are interesting since they capture some of the properties of a molecule in a single number. Hundreds of topological indices have been introduced and studied, starting with the seminal work by Wiener in which he used the sum of all shortest-path distances of a (molecular) graph for modeling physical properties of alkanes.

Chemical graph theory is the topology branch of mathematical chemistry which applies graph theory to mathematical modelling of chemical phenomena. The pioneers of chemical graph theory are Alexandru Balaban, Ante Graovac, Iván Gutman, Haruo Hosoya, Milan Randić and Nenad Trinajstić (also Harry Wiener and others). In 1988, it was reported that several hundred researchers worked in this area, producing about 500 articles annually. Several monographs have been written in the area, including the two-volume comprehensive text by Trinajstić, *Chemical Graph Theory*, that summarized the field up to mid-1980s. The adherents of the theory maintain that the properties of a chemical graph (i.e., a graph-theoretical representation of a molecule) give valuable insights into the chemical phenomena. Others contend that graphs play only a fringe role in chemical research. One variant of the theory is the representation of materials as infinite Euclidean graphs, particularly crystals by periodic graphs.

Mathematical chemistry is the term that has recently been coined to designate a new hybrid discipline which embraces both mathematics and chemistry. Practitioners of the discipline like to feel that their subject is far more than a simple admixture of appropriate mathematics applied to chemical problems. They believe it has an élan and a characteristic vitality which is all its own. Mathematical chemistry has been defined as that area of research engaged in the novel and nontrivial application of mathematics to chemistry; it concerns itself principally with the mathematical modeling of chemical phenomena and the gaining of valuable insights into chemical behaviour. Although its history can be traced back over 200 years, it is now being increasingly viewed as a new paradigm in chemistry. The truly interdisciplinary nature of this new enfant terrible is attested to by the fact that many of the great mathematicians of the past were intimately involved in the early stages of its development, including Cayley, Clifford, and Sylvester. At the present time there are

probably several thousand mathematical chemists worldwide and their numbers appear to be steadily increasing.

Problem Statement:

There has been a contiguous relationship between the chemical structures of drugs and the characteristics of alkenes, such as the boiling point, melting point, and enthalpy. Various topological indices have been used to predict the properties of drugs. In pharmaceutical drug design, the properties of molecular structure are essential for the achievement of a new product, and these properties can be identified from quantitative structure property relationship and quantitative structure activity relationship (QSPR/QSAR) modelling with topological indices. Thus, the properties of the compounds that have not been tested can be predicted and can save time and money, especially in drug discovery.

Objectives:

1. To study the structure of chemical compounds and computation of topological indices.
2. To define novel indices and use the same in QSPR/QSAR analysis.
3. To study the behaviour of chemical compounds using the topological indices
4. To compute the polynomials of the indices and determine for pharmaceutical drugs/chemical compounds.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction to graph theory

The development of graph theory has found its roots in pure mathematics. However, over a period of time it has discovered a whole variety of applications in different fields. Notable names during its development are Leonard Euler (1707-1783), Arthur Cayley (1821-1895) and James Sylvester (1817-1897). Now, it has become such an important tool that without this, the work becomes laborious and therefore proves hard to verify. For any area of interest in science and technology, there exists a necessity for the services of graph theory where connectivity has an important role to play. Important among them are optimization, communication, transport, health sciences, networks, analysis of social networks, electrical circuits and their applications. Topological indices is one of the most important topics in graph theory. There are various topological indices available and few of them are Zagreb indices, Zagreb Co-indices, Redefined Zagreb indices, Augmented Zagreb index, Geometric-Arithmetic index, Sum-Connectivity index, Harmonic index, Kekule index, Reciprocal Randić index, Reciprocal Reduced Randić index, Reduced Second Zagreb index, Adriatic index and Wiener index. A combination of graph theory and chemistry refers to chemical graph theory.

1.2 Applications of graph theory

Graph theory being a branch of Mathematics deals with networks spreading its applications in almost every field. It has widened its applications in chemistry, biology, computer science, engineering and many more areas. Mathematical chemistry is the term that has recently been coined to designate a new hybrid discipline which embraces both mathe-

matics and chemistry. Practitioners of the discipline like to feel that their subject is far more than a simple admixture of appropriate mathematics applied to chemical problems. They believe it has an elan and a characteristic vitality which is all its own. Mathematical chemistry has been defined as that area of research engaged in the novel and nontrivial application of mathematics to chemistry; it concerns itself principally with the mathematical modeling of chemical phenomena and the gaining of valuable insights into chemical behaviour. Mathematical chemistry has significant applications mainly in designing a drug for which QSAR/QSPR/QSTR(quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR)/quantitative structure-activity relationship/ quantitative structure toxicity relationship) analysis are used. To form a new drug, the properties of the excipients of the drug play a major role as it has to be consumed by living beings. Based on the properties and their analysis, the excipients and their quantity in the drug are decided. Once a new drug is made, it is sent for trials to check for side effects. After few trials, it is released for public use.

1.3 Topological indices and their applications

Topological indices are one of the most powerful tools in graph theory which helps in choosing the right excipient in the composition of a drug. Topological index is a numerical invariant which follows a certain rule. Based on the definition of the index, the topological index is computed for a graph, basically a molecular graph of a chemical compound. The first topological index was proposed by Harold Wiener which is named after him as Wiener index. This is the oldest and most popular topological index available. There are various indices available now proposed by various researchers. Each of these indices are significant in various applications.

Topological indices are categorized as

- Degree-based: Calculated using degree of a vertex.
- Distance-based: Computed using shortest paths between vertices.
- Degree and Distance-based: Computed using both degree and distance.
- Counting related: Calculated using the total number of vertices/edges close to the end vertices of each edge.

Some of the most commonly used topological indices in the literature are Wiener index [2], Connectivity indices [3], E-state index [4], Kappa shape index [5], Hosoya index [6], Balaban J index [7], Szeged index [8], information theory derived indices [9], Bonchev's index [10], Schultz's index [11], Zagreb indices [12], Randic indices, Atom-bond connectivity index, etc. Among these indices, degree-based indices are very interesting and studied well in literature.

The various degree-based topological indices are listed along with definitions and for complete review of these topological indices refer Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: List of degree-based Topological Indices

Topological Indices with Mathematical Expressions	
Randić index [13]	$R(G) = \chi(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{d_u \times d_v}}$
Reciprocal Randić index [14]	$RR(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{d_u \times d_v}$

Generalized Randić index [84]

$$R_\alpha(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u \times d_v)^\alpha$$

First and Second Zagreb indices [16]

$$M_1(G) = \sum_{u \in E(G)} d_u^2 = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u + d_v)$$

$$M_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (d_u \times d_v)$$

Harmonic index [17]

$$H(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{2}{d_u + d_v}$$

Inverse sum index [18]

$$I(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{d_u \times d_v}{d_u + d_v}$$

Forgotten topological index [19]

$$F(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [(d_u)^2 + (d_v)^2]$$

Atom-bond connectivity index [20]

$$ABC(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{\frac{d_u + d_v - 2}{d_u \times d_v}}$$

Geometric arithmetic index [21]

$$GA(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} 2 \frac{\sqrt{d_u \times d_v}}{d_u + d_v}$$

Augmented Zagreb index [22]

$$AZI(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left(\frac{d_u \times d_v}{d_u + d_v - 2} \right)^3$$

Sombor index [23]

$$SO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{(d_u)^2 + (d_v)^2}$$

SS index [56]

$$SS(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{\frac{d_u \times d_v}{d_u + d_v}}$$

GH index [25]

$$GH(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{(d_u + d_v)(\sqrt{d_u \times d_v})}{2}$$

In this work, Wiener index and Adriatic index are determined for a path attached to cycles of length ≥ 3 . The attached cycle is gradually moved through the set of vertices of the path to study the variation of the Wiener index. It is found that the Adriatic index is equal for all such graphs but the Wiener index, however, appears to be different in every case and lengths.

Also, cyclodextrin and its derivatives such as α, β, γ CDs are studied for which various degree and neighbourhood degree based TIs are computed through M-polynomial and NM-polynomial respectively and the comparison of the indices for all three types of cyclodextrins are presented which are of great importance in QSPR/QSAR studies.

Chapter 2

Variation of Adriatic and Wiener indices for different cycle lengths and paths

In this chapter, the Adriatic and Wiener indices are studied for varied cycle and path lengths. The outcome of a transformation of chemical structure into mathematical model, results in numerical descriptor. The chemical compound of a molecule is encoded into a useful number called molecular descriptor. These numerical descriptors have significant importance in the applications of physico-chemical properties of QSAR/QSPR/QSTR studies. Motivated from the work of Vukicevic, Wiener index and Adriatic index are determined for a path attached to cycles of length ≥ 3 . The attached cycle is gradually moved through the set of vertices of the path to study the variation of the Wiener index. It is found that the Adriatic index is equal for all such graphs but the Wiener index, however, appears to be different in every case and lengths.

This chapter is based on the publications of the papers entitled

¹ *Variation of Adriatic and Wiener indices for different cycle lengths and paths*, Discrete Mathematics Algorithms and Applications, doi: 10.1142/S1793830922501257

2.1 Introduction

Molecular descriptors are used to design and formulate drugs in chemistry which is of great importance in [29, 30, 34, 35, 66] QSAR and QSPR activities. Vukičević's [27] study shows that most of the molecular descriptors are bond additive which means they are calculated as the sum of the edge contributions and hence a large class of molecular descriptors which are analysed are named Adriatic indices. Also, Adriatic descriptors have been divided into three classes namely, extended Adriatic descriptors, variable Adriatic descriptors and discrete Adriatic descriptors. Vukičević et al., stated that the Wiener index is not an extended Adriatic index. In order to prove the above statement, we consider several cases of a cycle of length ≥ 3 attached to a path. In this regard, it is noted that the Adriatic index remains the same for each case but the Wiener index is different for each case. Hence, we affirm the statement of Vukičević that the Wiener index is not an extended Adriatic index [32]. A finite path of 3 vertices for u and 4 vertices for w are considered at first. Later, it is generalised with ' k ' vertices and ' l ' vertices respectively.

Wiener index was defined by Harold Wiener [2] for use in Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Quantitative Structure Property Relationship (QSPR). Wiener index is defined as

$$W(G) = \sum d(u, v)$$

where $d(u, v)$ is the distance between the vertices u and v taken over all the edges of the graph G [31, 33, 35].

Adriatic index If $e = uv$ is an edge in G then Adriatic index [27, 28] is defined as

$$A(G) = \sum_{e=uv \in E(G)} \gamma(\phi(u), \phi(v)) \cdot D_{u,v}(G)$$

where $D_{u,v}(G)$ is the number of edges of type $(u, v) \in G$.

2.2 Wiener index of Path with a cycle of length 3

Theorem 2.2.1. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 3 is attached between two vertices (w_1, u_1) , (u_1, u_2) , (u_2, u_3) , (w_1, w_2) , (w_2, w_3) and (w_3, w_4) , respectively denoted by G_1 , G_2 , G_3 , G_4 , G_5 and G_6 , are given by*

Figure 2.1: Path attached to cycle 3.

$$W(G_1) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 20k + 8l}{2} + 2kl + 75.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 16k + 12l}{2} + 2kl + 77.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 12k + 16l}{2} + 2kl + 87.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 24k + 4l}{2} + 2kl + 75.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 28k + 0l}{2} + 2kl + 83.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 32k - 4l}{2} + 2kl + 100.$$

Proof. A cycle of length 3 is attached to a vertex v where two paths w_1, w_2, \dots, w_l and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are attached on either side of the vertex v as shown in the Figure 2.1. The graph for the vertex v , positioned initially between (w_1, u_1) , is denoted by G_1 . The corresponding Wiener index is denoted as $W(G_1)$. After calculation of the Wiener index at this position, the position of vertex v is moved by one distance in the directions of path u_k first and then in the direction of w_l . At this stage, the extreme positions are not considered. All such cases are taken up after the discussion of the vertex v lying between u and w . Taking into consideration all such involved edges and their respective distances for all positions excepting the extreme positions, the Wiener indices are given by,

$$W(G_1) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 20k + 8l}{2} + 2kl + 75.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 16k + 12l}{2} + 2kl + 77.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 12k + 16l}{2} + 2kl + 87.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 24k + 4l}{2} + 2kl + 75.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 28k + 0l}{2} + 2kl + 83.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{10k^2 + 10l^2 + 32k - 4l}{2} + 2kl + 100.$$

□

2.3 Wiener index of path with a cycle of length 4

Theorem 2.3.1. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 4 is attached similar to the figure shown in Figure 2.1 between two vertices $(w_1, u_1), (u_1, u_2), (u_2, u_3), (w_1, w_2), (w_2, w_3)$ and (w_3, w_4) , respectively denoted by G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5 and G_6 , are given by*

$$W(G_1) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 25k + 13l}{2} + 2kl + 117.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 31k + 7l}{2} + 2kl + 154.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 37k + l}{2} + 2kl + 136.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 43k - 5l}{2} + 2kl + 155.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 13k + 25l}{2} + 2kl + 140.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 19k + 19l}{2} + 2kl + 130.$$

Proof. A cycle of length 4 is attached to a vertex v where two paths w_1, w_2, \dots, w_l and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are attached on either side of the vertex v as shown in the Figure 2.1. The graph for the vertex v , positioned initially between (w_1, u_1) , is denoted by G_1 . The

corresponding Wiener index is denoted as $W(G_1)$. After calculation of the Wiener index at this position, the position of vertex v is moved by one distance in the directions of path u_k first and then in the direction of w_l . At this stage, the extreme positions are not considered. All such cases are taken up after the discussion of the vertex v lying between u and w . Taking into consideration all such involved edges and their respective distances for all positions excepting the extreme positions, the Wiener indices are given by,

$$W(G_1) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 25k + 13l}{2} + 2kl + 117.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 31k + 7l}{2} + 2kl + 154.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 37k + l}{2} + 2kl + 136.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 43k - 5l}{2} + 2kl + 155.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 13k + 25l}{2} + 2kl + 140.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{11k^2 + 11l^2 + 19k + 19l}{2} + 2kl + 130.$$

□

2.4 Wiener index of path with a cycle of length 5

Theorem 2.4.1. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 5 is attached between two vertices $(w_1, u_1), (u_1, u_2), (u_2, u_3), (w_1, w_2), (w_2, w_3)$ and (w_3, w_4) , respectively denoted by G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5 and G_6 , are given by*

$$W(G_1) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 30k + 18l}{2} + 2kl + 166.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 22k + 34l}{2} + 2kl + 191.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 12k + 32l}{2} + 2kl + 205.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 38k + 10l}{2} + 2kl + 167.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 46k + 2l}{2} + 2kl + 198.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 54k - 6l}{2} + 2kl + 225.$$

Proof. A cycle of length 5 is attached to a vertex v where two paths w_1, w_2, \dots, w_l and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are attached on either side of the vertex v as shown in the Figure 2.1. The graph for the vertex v , positioned initially between (w_1, u_1) , is denoted by G_1 . The corresponding Wiener index is denoted as $W(G_1)$. After calculation of the Wiener index at this position, the position of vertex v is moved by one distance in the directions of path u_k first and then in the direction of w_l . At this stage, the extreme positions are not considered. All such cases are taken up after the discussion of the vertex v lying between u and w . Taking into consideration all such involved edges and their respective distances for all positions excepting the extreme positions, the Wiener indices are given by,

$$W(G_1) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 30k + 18l}{2} + 2kl + 166.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 22k + 34l}{2} + 2kl + 191.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 12k + 32l}{2} + 2kl + 205.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 38k + 10l}{2} + 2kl + 167.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 46k + 2l}{2} + 2kl + 198.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{12k^2 + 12l^2 + 54k - 6l}{2} + 2kl + 225.$$

□

2.5 Wiener index of path with a cycle of length 6

Theorem 2.5.1. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 6 is attached between two vertices $(w_1, u_1), (u_1, u_2), (u_2, u_3), (w_1, w_2), (w_2, w_3)$ and (w_3, w_4) , are respectively denoted by G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5 and G_6 given by*

$$W(G_1) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 37k + 25l}{2} + 2kl + 235.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 27k + 35l}{2} + 2kl + 250.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 17k + 45l}{2} + 2kl + 278.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 47k + 15l}{2} + 2kl + 240.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 59k + 3l}{2} + 2kl + 247.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 67k - 6l}{2} + 2kl + 210.$$

Proof. A cycle of length 6 is attached to a vertex v where two paths w_1, w_2, \dots, w_l and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are attached on either side of the vertex v as shown in the Figure 2.1. The graph for the vertex v , positioned initially between (w_1, u_1) , is denoted by G_1 . The corresponding Wiener index is denoted as $W(G_1)$. After calculation of the Wiener index at this position, the position of vertex v is moved by one distance in the directions of path u_k first and then in the direction of w_l . At this stage, the extreme positions are not considered. All such cases are taken up after the discussion of the vertex v lying between u and w . Taking into consideration all such involved edges and their respective distances for all positions excepting the extreme positions, the Wiener indices are given by,

$$W(G_1) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 37k + 25l}{2} + 2kl + 235.$$

$$W(G_2) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 27k + 35l}{2} + 2kl + 250.$$

$$W(G_3) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 17k + 45l}{2} + 2kl + 278.$$

$$W(G_4) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 47k + 15l}{2} + 2kl + 240.$$

$$W(G_5) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 59k + 3l}{2} + 2kl + 247.$$

$$W(G_6) = \frac{13k^2 + 13l^2 + 67k - 6l}{2} + 2kl + 210.$$

□

2.6 Wiener index and Adriatic index at the Extreme positions of the cycle attached to a path

Theorem 2.6.1. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 3 is attached at the extreme positions of the path namely u_k denoted by G_k and w_l denoted by G_l , are given by*

$$W(G_k) = \frac{9k^2 + 9l^2 + 5k - 5l}{2} + 4kl + 68.$$

$$W(G_l) = \frac{9k^2 + 9l^2 + 17k - 17l}{2} + 4kl + 74.$$

Proof. As the cycle of length 3 is attached to the extreme position at the vertex u_k , the vertex v is not taken into consideration. Therefore, the path of length $(k + l)$ will be of length $(k + l - 1)$ as the vertex v is not included. Similarly, the cycle of length 3 is attached next to the other extreme position of the path at the vertex w_l .

Calculating the Wiener index for these cases will result in

$$W(G_k) = \frac{9k^2 + 9l^2 + 5k - 5l}{2} + 4kl + 68.$$

$$W(G_l) = \frac{9k^2 + 9l^2 + 17k - 17l}{2} + 4kl + 74.$$

□

Theorem 2.6.2. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 4 is attached at the extreme positions of the path namely u_k denoted by G_k and w_l denoted by G_l , are given by*

$$W(G_k) = \frac{7k^2 + 10l^2 + 3k + 16l}{2} + 2kl + 102.$$

$$W(G_l) = \frac{10k^2 + 7l^2 + 32k - 7l}{2} + 2kl + 150.$$

Proof. Proof is similar to the one obtained in the previous theorem. \square

Theorem 2.6.3. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 5 is attached at the extreme positions of the path namely u_k denoted by G_k and w_l denoted by G_l , are given by*

$$W(G_k) = \frac{7k^2 + 11l^2 + 3k + 25l}{2} + 2kl + 187.$$

$$W(G_l) = \frac{11k^2 + 7l^2 + 43k - 7l}{2} + 2kl + 210.$$

Proof. Proof is similar to the proof that was obtained in the previous theorem. \square

Theorem 2.6.4. *The Wiener indices of the path, for which a cycle of length 6 is attached at the extreme positions of the path namely u_k denoted by G_k and w_l denoted by G_l , are given by*

$$W(G_k) = \frac{7k^2 + 12l^2 + 3k + 36l}{2} + 2kl + 255.$$

$$W(G_l) = \frac{12k^2 + 7l^2 + 46k - 7l}{2} + 2kl + 283.$$

Proof. Proof is similar to the proof of that obtained in the previous theorem. \square

2.7 Adriatic index for paths

Theorem 2.7.1. *The Adriatic index of the path, for which a cycle of length 3 is attached, is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l - 3)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 2\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 4\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(4)).$$

Proof. As the path shown in Figure 2.1, has $(k+l+3)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 4)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l-3)$, 2 and 4. Using this data in the calculation of Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for all graphs namely, G_i , where $i = 1$ to 6. \square

Theorem 2.7.2. *The Adriatic index of the path, for which a cycle of length 4 is attached, is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l - 2)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 2\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 4\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(4)).$$

Proof. Same as the path shown in Figure 2.1, the cycle of length 4 has $(k+l+4)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 4)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l-2)$, 2 and 4. Using this data in the calculation of Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for all the graphs namely, G_i , where $i = 1$ to 6. \square

Theorem 2.7.3. *The Adriatic index of the path, for which a cycle of length 5 is attached, is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l - 1)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 2\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 4\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(4)).$$

Proof. Same as the path shown in the Figure 2.1, the cycle of length 5 has $(k+l+5)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 4)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l-1)$, 2 and 4. Using this data in the calculation of Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for all graphs namely, G_i , where $i = 1$ to 6. \square

Theorem 2.7.4. *The Adriatic index of the path, for which a cycle of length 6 is attached, is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 2\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 4\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(4)).$$

Proof. Same as the path shown in the Figure 2.1, the cycle of length 6 has $(k+l+6)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 4)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l)$, 2 and 4. Using this data in the calculation of Adriatic index, it is clear that the total

number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for all graphs namely, G_i , where $i = 1$ to 6. \square

2.8 Adriatic index for paths where cycle is attached at extreme positions

Theorem 2.8.1. *The Adriatic index of the path for which a cycle of length 3 attached at the extreme positions is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l - 2)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 1\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 3\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(3)).$$

Proof. The cycle of length 3 attached at the extreme positions has $(k+l+2)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 3)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l-2)$, 1 and 3. Using this data in the calculation of Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for both extreme positions of the graphs namely, G_i , where $i = k$ and $i = l$. \square

Theorem 2.8.2. *The Adriatic index of the path for which a cycle of length 4 attached at the extreme positions is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l - 1)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 1\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 3\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(3)).$$

Proof. The cycle of length 4 attached at the extreme positions has $(k+l+3)$ edges in total, there are $(2, 2)$, $(1, 2)$ and $(2, 3)$ edges only. Their numbers are respectively, $(k+l-1)$, 1 and 3. Using this data in the Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for both extreme positions of the graphs namely, G_i , where $i = k$ and $i = l$. \square

Theorem 2.8.3. *The Adriatic index of the path for which a cycle of length 5 attached at the extreme positions is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 1\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 3\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(3)).$$

Proof. The cycle of length 4 attached at the extreme positions has $(k+l+4)$ edges in

total, there are (2, 2), (1, 2) and (2, 3) edges only. Their numbers are respectively, (k+1), 1 and 3. Using this data in the Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for both extreme positions of the graphs namely, G_i , where $i = k$ and $i = l$. \square

Theorem 2.8.4. *The Adriatic index of the path for which a cycle of length 6 attached at the extreme positions is given by*

$$A(G_i) = (k + l + 1)\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(2)) + 1\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 3\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(3)).$$

Proof. The cycle of length 4 attached at the extreme positions has (k+1+5) edges in total, there are (2, 2), (1, 2) and (2, 3) edges only. Their numbers are respectively, (k+1+1), 1 and 3. Using this data in the Adriatic index, it is clear that the total number of edges in the mentioned edge vertices equals the total number of edges in the path. Adriatic index remains the same for both extreme positions of the graphs namely, G_i , where $i = k$ and $i = l$. \square

2.9 Conclusions

- The Wiener index in general for all vertices excepting the extreme vertices can be put in the form

$$W(G) = \frac{(n + 7)(k^2 + l^2) + 4kl}{2} + a(k + bl + c).$$

where

$n \rightarrow$ the number of vertices of the cycle considered.

k and $l \rightarrow$ the paths attached on either side of the cycle.

a, b and $c \rightarrow$ arbitrary constants.

Three cases are considered where x could be greater than unity, less than unity and equal to unity.

- Correspondingly, the path l is greater than path k , is less than path k and equal to path k .
- Suppose $l = xk$; x is greater than unity. The above equation gets modified as

$$W(G) = \frac{k^2[(n+7)(1+x^2)+4x]}{2} + k(a+bx) + c.$$

- Suppose $k = xl$; x is greater than unity. The above equation gets modified as

$$W(G) = \frac{l^2[(n+7)(1+x^2)+4x]}{2} + l(ax+b) + c.$$

- Suppose the paths are equal. The above equation gets modified as

$$W(G) = \frac{(n+11)k^2}{2} + ak + b.$$

- The Adriatic index can be generalised, for the vertex v lying in the middle as

$$A(G) = (k+l+n-6)\gamma((\phi(2), \phi(2))) + 2\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 4\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(4)).$$

- Similarly, the Adriatic index at the extreme positions, can be written as

$$A(G) = (k+l+n-5)\gamma((\phi(2), \phi(2))) + 1\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + 3\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(3)).$$

- Combining the above two equations, we have

$$A(G) = (k+l+n-6+e)\gamma((\phi(2), \phi(2))) + (1+m)\gamma(\phi(1), \phi(2)) + v\gamma(\phi(2), \phi(v)).$$

where $e=0$ for middle positions of the vertex and $e=1$ for the extreme positions of the vertex; $m=1$ for middle positions of the vertex and $m=0$ for the extreme positions of the vertex; $v=4$ for middle positions of the vertex and $v=3$ for the extreme positions of the vertex.

- Thus it is affirmed that the Wiener index is not an extended Adriatic index for any of the shapes or path lengths considered.

Chapter 3

Comparative Study of Degree-based Molecular Descriptors of Cyclodextrins through M-polynomial and NM-polynomial

In this chapter, a detailed study on chemical compound, Cyclodextrins and their derivatives are studied. Cyclodextrins are natural oligosaccharides used to increase the solubility of drugs. It has numerous applications in drug discovery, food storage and other fields. Loftsson et al. explained about applications of Cyclodextrins (CDs) in administering the drugs through various ways. Jansook et al. has given insights into the structure, physicochemical properties and pharmaceutical applications of CDs. In the present work, cyclodextrin and its derivatives such as α, β, γ CDs are studied for which various degree and neighbourhood degree based TIs are computed through M-polynomial and NM-polynomial respectively and the comparison of the indices for all three types of cyclodextrins are presented which are of great importance in QSPR/QSAR studies.

This chapter is based on the publication of the paper entitled

²*Comparative Study of Degree-based Molecular Descriptors of Cyclodextrins through M-polynomial and NM-polynomial*, Journal of the Indian Chemical Society (accepted), 2023.

3.1 Introduction

In the present scenario, there is an increasing demand for healthier food products as large population suffer from various ailments due to several regions such as food preservatives, environmental changes, pollution etc.,. This prompts the researchers to find new ways to improve food products and storing of the same. Healthier food products have demand in society leading to improvise the new ways to research. By fortifying foods with bio-active compound, this demand can satisfy. Also, there is a great demand for organic foods which uses natural ingredients in producing them without any harmful pesticides. A perfect alternative to enhance/reduce distinct biomolecule characteristics that have helped to get great results in food science are CDs. To manage these strategies, CDs are used [41, 42].

In 1891, Antoine Villiers first discovered the crystals dextrins which he described in his first publication. It was obtained by potato starch using chemical process. Later, Franz explained about the preparation and purification of dextrins in his publication made in 1903. Post 30 years of these findings, Freudenberg and his team explained about its structure. In the late 1940s, Friedrich Cramer defined the characteristics of dextrins and named it as cyclodextrins. Cramer found the process of purifying and separating the derivatives of cyclodextrins, namely α -CD, β -CD and γ -CD.

Cyclodextrins (CDs) are oligosaccharides with a lipophilic core chamber and a hydrophilic outer surface. CDs have glucose units linked to $\alpha - (1,4)$ with cone shape. In food industry, the most common glucose units are 6, 7, 8 called alpha(α), beta(β) and gamma(γ) CDs respectively [43].

Figure 1, represents the molecular structure of CDs for n units. By giving the values for $n = 1, 2, 3$ the derivatives of CDs are obtained known as α, β, γ CDs respectively.

To increase the solubility in poorly soluble drugs, CDs are used. CDs improve drug delivery both in humans and animals. Drugs must be lipophilic in order to permeate biological membranes and be pharmacologically active. CDs were discovered a century ago, but these are used more recent years because of the aqueous solubility used in drugs for increasing their bio-availability and stability. There are numerous applications of CDs including the usage of CDs to reduce gastrointestinal problems

caused by drug irritation. It is used to convert liquid drugs to amorphous powder form and used to prevent drug-drug interactions.

A pharmacist should be aware of merits and demerits of the excipients used in designing a drug. Depending on the physicochemical properties such as solubility, stability etc., the excipients are chosen for forming a drug. Sublingual drug delivery is the structured way to bypass hepatic first-pass metabolism. This process helps the drug to dissolve in saliva to enter into systematic circulation. The therapeutic dose must be relatively small as it must dissolve in small volume of saliva present in the mouth and generally dissolution enhancers must be applied [44, 45].

The drug delivery can be done through nasal, pulmonary, injectable, ophthalmic and dermal. Nasal drug delivery is an effective way to bypass the hepatic metabolism. Nasal mucosa has good permeability properties for the systematic delivery of peptides. CDs increase the solubility of lipophilic drugs in nasal formulations. For nasal delivery, CDs act as penetration enhancers where proteins are administered in the form of pills/medicine. To treat asthmatic or other lung diseases, the pulmonary administration of drugs are used. The drug is delivered to the gastrointestinal tract via the lungs. Because the lungs have a large surface area, blood flow is high and enzymatic activity is low, resulting in effective drug absorption. The removal of bad smell from the drugs is possible with the usage of CDs.

There are limitations of injectable formulations of being lipophilic water-insoluble, drug precipitation, pain, inflammation and haemolysis. However, organic solvents can be replaced by aqueous CDs solutions. CDs containing formulations are in great use when research on new drugs are studied with in and out side living organism which are refereed to as in vitro and in vivo screening respectively. The low viscosity aqueous eye drops are administered in ophthalmology. CDs have been used to increase the dissolved drug at the lipophilic membrane surface and reduce ophthalmic drug irritation.

The stratum corneum is the primary barrier to drug absorption into or through the skin. Dermal drugs use penetration enhancers to penetrate the skin's outermost layer. CDs reduce drug delivery through excised skin, increase drug delivery through aqueous layers, but do not improve drug delivery through lipophilic barriers.

The research shows that stability of steroid, anticancer agents, prodrugs and prostaglandins

can be amended using cyclodextrins in the formulation of the drugs. The drug can be stabilized in their solid dosage forms using CDs.

Chemical graphs are non-numerical representation of chemical structure with many applications in computing structural descriptors for QSAR/QSPR modelling [46, 47]. Chemical compounds are modelled as graphs, atoms and their respective bonds are considered as vertices and edges respectively. Usually, hydrogen atoms are suppressed in chemical graphs. Topological indices have been proved to be sufficiently rich in information in the aspects of 3D structural information of compounds [48, 49].

Chemistry is the key source in the application of graph theory in every field. Graphical invariants play a significant role and provides a reserve of data to facilitate the chemists in the development of the study. The graph invariant/topological index forecasts the range of molecular properties of a compound by defining the graph topology of the structure of the molecule [50, 51].

Topological graph measures play a major role in characterizing graphs quantitatively. These measures may be categorized as information theoretic and non-information theoretic. These can be further divided into graph invariants involving vertex degrees, distance based, eigen values etc. The other categorization results in symmetry measures, cyclicity measures and branching measures. There have been a huge number of topological graph measures that are being developed and applied in mathematical chemistry, bioinformatics, computer science etc., extensively [52].

A notable number of drugs are manufactured every year and they are released in market after clinical trials. Initially, there were a huge number of tests were needed to detect the side effects and toxicity on human body which needs large laboratories and amount. A large quantity of the compounds was compared with their experiment results to their molecular structure to draw the drug properties. These properties are linked to their molecular structure.

In the recent years, significant contributions are made in the recent years in the study of QSAR/QSPR modelling using the concept of topological descriptors [53, 54, 55, 56, 57]. A combination of topological indices with hydrophobicity results in developing the relations of QSAR/QSPR. Topological descriptors are used to discriminate between the drug and non-drug compounds [58, 59]. The indices help in discovering of large number of compounds in the combinatorial syntheses and rapid

screening of toxicity of the compounds. These are used more, since they are cost effective in designing of efficacious drugs with the risk of new chemicals. Topological indices (TIs) have gained large popularity because of its rapid computability in drawing a lot of information about the molecular structure of chemical compounds without performing any experiment [60, 61, 62, 63].

Changes in chemical structure cause systematic changes in organic compounds physicochemical properties and biological activities. A computational chemist is interested in the formulation of quantitative relations and structural features of compounds in deriving relationships in diagnostic and mechanistic interpretation/prediction of properties/activities [64]. TI helps the chemists in the addition of a chemical compound in the composition of a drug based on range of the index. Every index will have a range in which beyond the upper limit of the range, the compound may not be advisable to be included in the drug formation that may be consumed by living beings.

Seven decades ago Harold Wiener proposed Wiener index after which the topological indices were evolved. At present, there are various indices defined by many researchers worldwide [65, 66]. Still the studies are on the existing and novel indices. The study of graph theory has advanced in a rapid way because of its varied applications in many fields.

Topological indices are useful in the study of QSPR studies by correlating the physical properties to its molecular structure. Wiener first operated Wiener index on structure property studies and found that this index was the perfect suit with the boiling point of the alkane [67]. Several studies used this index to link the physical and chemical properties of the compounds resulted in the development of graph theory in chemistry.

After the introduction of Wiener index, many famous indices were introduced are still found to be the efficient ones. One of the oldest indices after Wiener was the Randic index. Followed by Randic index, Bollobas et.al. [68] designed the generalised version of Randic index. An alternative of the Randic index was first proposed by Fajtlowicz was the Harmonic index [69, 70].

The most oldest and very well-known indices were introduced by Gutman known as Zagreb indices found very successful in determining the total π -electron energy of molecules [71]. Later, there were many versions of Zagreb indices by various

researchers. Ranjini et.al. [72] introduced redefined Zagreb indices includes three versions of the indices. It has been used in many studies for various chemical compounds.

Forgotten index was found to be useful in predicting the performance identical to that of the old well-known Zagreb indices. It was introduced by Gutman and studies on this index was carried out jointly by Furtula with Gutman [73, 74]. Recently, Vukicevic introduced a series of topological indices by the concept of bond additive modelling. One of them was the symmetric division index found to be the best indicator of aggregate surface area for octane isomers and polychlorobiphenyls [75, 76].

A new concept of neighborhood degree-based indices were found to be very effective in predicting the physico-chemical properties of the compounds. Zagreb index has its neighborhood version introduced by Ghorbani popularly known as the third version of Zagreb index. The enhanced version of Zagreb index was introduced by Hosamani called Sanskruti index associated with the entropy of octane isomers. Thereafter, various topological indices were introduced on the concept of neighborhood degree[77].

In this work, oligosaccharides called Cyclodextrins and its derivatives known as α, β, γ -CDs are modelled as molecular graphs. Consider a graph $G = (V, E)$ with vertices V , represented as atoms and edges E represented as bond respectively. Refer [78, 79] for standard notations and terminologies of graphs.

Initially, M-polynomial and NM-polynomial are found for molecular graph of cyclodextrin and various degree-based and neighborhood degree-based indices are derived using the respective polynomials. The indices are $M_1(G)$, $M_2(G)$, ${}^m M_2(G)$, $ReZG_3(G)$, $F(G)$, $R(G)$, $RR(G)$, $SDD(G)$, $I(G)$, $H(G)$, $A(G)$ and the neighborhood versions of the above indices are determined.

3.2 M-polynomial & NM-polynomial

Graph theory has a large collection of tools such as graph invariants, eigen values, polynomials and many more play a significant role in varied applications. Polynomials play a crucial role not only in mathematics but also in medicine and other fields. For example, Hosoya polynomials [80], Zagreb polynomials, Zagreb polyno-

mials which give rise to one or two indices. In graph theory, Hosoya first introduced polynomial which is distance-based polynomial. Hosoya polynomials have various chemical applications and all the distance-based indices can be derived from it. Later, Harary polynomial was introduced was also distance-based using which, Harary index may be derived. Solving a general polynomial includes the evaluation of the polynomial composed of derivatives or integrals or both at a particular point [81, 82, 83, 84].

From Hosoya polynomial, Wiener index, hyper Wiener index and other variants of Wiener index may be derived. M-polynomial is new concept of polynomial from which the degree-based topological indices are derived. Lot of studies are being carried out on M-polynomial. 11 degree-based TIs are derived using a single M-polynomial. The significance of this polynomial is that it can give exact forms of most of the degree-based indices. A brisk advancement in this concept is being made. Following the concept of M-polynomial [85], neighborhood degree-based polynomial was introduced called NM-polynomial [86]. Using NM-polynomial, 11 neighborhood degree based TIs are derived. The properties of these when analysed gives a perception in the study of topological descriptors [87, 88, 89].

In this study, M-polynomial and NM-polynomial are computed for cyclodextrins(CDs) from which degree-based and neighborhood degree-based TIs are derived respectively. CDs have significant applications in the drug field. They are used in the drugs to increase the solubility of drugs. CDs were discovered a century ago, but it is more in use recently because of the aqueous solubility used in drugs for increasing their bioavailability and stability. There are numerous applications of cyclodextrins, includes the usage of CDs to reduce gastrointestinal problems caused by drug irritation. It is used to convert liquid drugs to amorphous powder form and used to prevent drug-drug interactions.

Definition 3.2.1. For a simple connected graph G , the M -polynomial is defined as,

$$M(G; x, y) = \sum_{i \leq j} m_{ij}(G) x^i y^j$$

where m_{ij} represents the number of edges $\vartheta\omega \in E(G)$ such that $\{d(\vartheta), d(\omega)\} = \{i, j\}$. Here $d(\vartheta)$, $d(\omega)$ represent the degrees of the vertices ϑ and ω in the graph G .

Definition 3.2.2. For a simple connected graph G , the NM -polynomial is defined as,

$$NM(G; x, y) = \sum_{i \leq j} m_{ij}^*(G) x^i y^j$$

where m_{ij}^* represents the number of edges $\vartheta\omega \in E(G)$ such that, $\{nd(\vartheta), nd(\omega)\} = \{i, j\}$. Here $nd(\vartheta)$, $nd(\omega)$ represent the neighborhood degree sum of the vertices ϑ and ω in the graph G .

Table 3.1: The relation between various TI's with M-polynomial & NM-polynomial.

Topological index	Formula	Derivation from
$g(\mu(\vartheta), \mu(\omega))$ $f(x, y) = M(G; x, y)$ or $NM(G; x, y)$		
M_1/NM_1	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega)$	$(D_x + D_y)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
M_2/NM_2	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)$	$(D_x D_y)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
${}^m M_2/{}^m NM_2$	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)}$	$(S_x S_y)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
$ReZG_3/ND_3$	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)(\mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega))$	$D_x D_y (D_x + D_y)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
F/NF	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \mu^2(\vartheta) + \mu^2(\omega)$	$(D_x^2 + D_y^2)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
R_k/NR_k	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)\}^k$	$(D_x^k D_y^k)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
RR_k/NRR_k	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)\}^k}$	$(S_x^k S_y^k)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
SDD/ND_5	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \frac{\mu^2(\vartheta) + \mu^2(\omega)}{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)}$	$(D_x S_y + S_x D_y)(f(x, y))_{x=1=y}$
H/NH	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \frac{\mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega)}{\mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega)}$	$2S_x J(f(x, y))_{x=1}$
I/NI	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \frac{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)}{\mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega)}$	$S_x J D_x D_y (f(x, y))_{x=1}$
A/S	$\sum_{\vartheta\omega \in E(G)} \left\{ \frac{\mu(\vartheta)\mu(\omega)}{\mu(\vartheta) + \mu(\omega) - 2} \right\}^3$	$S_x^3 Q_{-2} J D_x^3 D_y^3 (f(x, y))_{x=1}$
where		
$D_x = x \frac{\partial(f(x, y))}{\partial x},$	$D_y = y \frac{\partial(f(x, y))}{\partial y},$	$S_x = \int_0^x \frac{f(t, y)}{t} dt,$
$S_y = \int_0^y \frac{f(x, t)}{t} dt,$	$J(f(x, y)) = f(x, x),$	$Q_\beta(f(x, y)) = x^\beta f(x, y).$

For degree-based TIs: $\mu(\vartheta) = d(\vartheta)$, $\mu(\omega) = d(\omega)$, $f(x, y) = M(G; x, y)$ and for neighborhood degree based TIs: $\mu(\vartheta) = nd(\vartheta)$, $\mu(\omega) = nd(\omega)$, $f(x, y) = NM(G; x, y)$.

3.3 Methodology

The molecular structures of cyclodextrins & its derivatives were modelled as molecular graphs in the current work. There are several degree and neighborhood-based graph invariants are computed. These indices are then compared numerically and presented. Vertex partition, edge partition and combinatorial computation methods were employed to compute the aforementioned indices.

Figure 3.1: Molecular structure of CDs.

3.4 Results for M-polynomial of Cyclodextrins (CDs)

Details of degrees of end vertices and their edges from Figure 3.1 are tabulated in Table 3.2 for the molecular graph of CDs.

Table 3.2: Edge partitioning of a molecular graph of CDs based on the degrees of each edge's end vertices.

(d_ϑ, d_ω) where $\vartheta\omega \in E(G)$	No. of edges
$E_1 = (1, 2)$	$n + 5$
$E_2 = (1, 3)$	$2n + 10$
$E_3 = (2, 3)$	$5n + 25$
$E_4 = (3, 3)$	$4n + 20$

Consider a molecular graph G for Cyclodextrin, by employing M-polynomial definition and Table 3.2, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 M(G, x, y) &= \sum_{i \leq j} E_{i,j}(G) x^i y^j \\
 &= \sum_{1 \leq 2} |E_{1,2}|(G) x^1 y^2 + \sum_{1 \leq 3} |E_{1,3}|(G) x^1 y^3 + \sum_{2 \leq 3} |E_{2,3}|(G) x^2 y^3 + \sum_{3 \leq 3} |E_{3,3}|(G) x^3 y^3 \\
 &= (n + 5)x^1 y^2 + (2n + 10)x^1 y^3 + (5n + 25)x^2 y^3 + (4n + 20)x^3 y^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

We have, the M-polynomial of a graph G for Cyclodextrin as

$$M(G; x, y) = f(x, y) = (n + 5)x^1 y^2 + (2n + 10)x^1 y^3 + (5n + 25)x^2 y^3 + (4n + 20)x^3 y^3.$$

Figure 3.2: M-polynomial of Cyclodextrin 3D plot.

then

$$D_x f(x, y) = 1(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 1(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 2(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 3(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$D_y f(x, y) = 2(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 3(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 3(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 3(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$(D_x + D_y)f(x, y) = 3(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 4(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 5(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 6(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$D_y D_x f(x, y) = 2(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 3(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 6(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 9(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$(D_x^2 + D_y^2)f(x, y) = 5(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 10(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 13(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 18(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$D_x^k D_y^k f(x, y) = 2^k(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 3^k(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 6^k(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 9^k(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$D_x D_y (D_x + D_y)f(x, y) = 6(n + 5)x^1y^2 + 12(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + 30(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + 54(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$S_x S_y f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{1}{3}(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + \frac{1}{6}(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + \frac{1}{9}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$S_x^k S_y^k f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2^k}(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{1}{3^k}(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + \frac{1}{6^k}(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + \frac{1}{9^k}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$(S_y D_x + S_x D_y)f(x, y) = \frac{5}{2}(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{10}{3}(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + \frac{13}{6}(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + \frac{18}{9}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$2S_x J f(x, y) = \frac{2}{3}(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{2}{4}(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + \frac{2}{5}(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + \frac{2}{6}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$S_x J D_x D_y f(x, y) = \frac{2}{3}(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{3}{4}(2n + 10)x^1y^3 + \frac{6}{5}(5n + 25)x^2y^3 + \frac{19}{6}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

$$S_x^3 Q_{-2} J D_x^3 D_y^3 f(x, y) = 8(n + 5)x^1y^2 + \frac{729}{64}(4n + 20)x^3y^3,$$

Using the above results in Table 3.1, we obtain

$$M_1(G) = (D_x + D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 60n + 300,$$

$$M_2(G) = (D_x D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 74n + 370,$$

$${}^m M_2(G) = (S_x S_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 2.444n + 12.222,$$

$$ReZG_3(G) = D_x D_y (D_x + D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 396n + 1980,$$

$$F(G) = (D_x^2 + D_y^2)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 162n + 810,$$

$$R_k(G) = (D_x^k D_y^k)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = (n + 5)2^k + (2n + 10)3^k + (5n + 25)6^k + (4n + 20)9^k,$$

$$RR_k(G) = (S_x^k S_y^k)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = (n + 5)\frac{1}{2^k} + (2n + 10)\frac{1}{3^k} + (5n + 25)\frac{1}{6^k} + (4n + 20)\frac{1}{9^k},$$

$$SSD(G) = (D_x S_y + S_x D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 28n + 140,$$

$$H(G) = 2S_x J f(x, y)|_{x=1} = 5n + 25,$$

$$I(G) = S_x J D_x D_y f(x, y)|_{x=1} = 14.167n + 70.833,$$

$$A(G) = S_x^3 Q_{-2} J D_x^3 D_y^3 f(x, y)|_{x=1} = 100.312n + 501.563.$$

3.5 Results for NM-polynomial of Cyclodextrins (CDs)

Details of neighbour degrees of end vertices and their edges from Figure 3.1 are tabulated in Table 3.3 for the molecular graph of CDs.

Table 3.3: The edge partitioning of a molecular graph of CDs based on the neighbour degrees of each edge's end vertices.

(S_ϑ, S_ω) where $\vartheta\omega \in E(G)$	No. of edges
$E_1 = (2, 4)$	$n + 5$
$E_2 = (3, 7)$	$2n + 10$
$E_3 = (4, 7)$	$n + 5$
$E_4 = (6, 7)$	$3n + 15$
$E_5 = (6, 8)$	$n + 5$
$E_6 = (7, 7)$	$2n + 10$
$E_7 = (7, 8)$	$2n + 10$

Consider a molecular graph G for Cyclodextrins, by employing NM-polynomial

definition and Table 3.3, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
NM(G, x, y) &= \sum_{i \leq j} E_{i,j}(G) x^i y^j \\
&= \sum_{2 \leq 4} |E_{2,4}|(G) x^2 y^4 + \sum_{3 \leq 7} |E_{3,7}|(G) x^3 y^7 + \sum_{4 \leq 7} |E_{4,7}|(G) x^4 y^7 + \sum_{6 \leq 7} |E_{6,7}|(G) x^6 y^7 \\
&+ \sum_{6 \leq 8} |E_{6,8}|(G) x^6 y^8 + \sum_{7 \leq 7} |E_{7,7}|(G) x^7 y^7 + \sum_{7 \leq 8} |E_{7,8}|(G) x^7 y^8 \\
&= (n + 5)x^2 y^4 + (2n + 10)x^3 y^7 + (n + 5)x^4 y^7 + (3n + 15)x^6 y^7 + (n + 5)x^6 y^8 \\
&+ (2n + 10)x^7 y^7 + (2n + 10)x^7 y^8.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 3.3: NM-polynomial of Cyclodextrin 3D plot.

We have, the NM-polynomial of cyclcodextrin graph G as

$$\begin{aligned}
NM(G; x, y) = f(x, y) &= (n + 5)x^2 y^4 + (2n + 10)x^3 y^7 + (n + 5)x^4 y^7 + (3n + 15)x^6 y^7 \\
&+ (n + 5)x^6 y^8 + (2n + 10)x^7 y^7 + (2n + 10)x^7 y^8.
\end{aligned}$$

then

$$D_x f(x, y) = 2(n+5)x^2y^4 + 3(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 4(n+5)x^4y^7 + 6(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 6(n+5)x^6y^8 + 7(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 7(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$D_y f(x, y) = 4(n+5)x^2y^4 + 7(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 7(n+5)x^4y^7 + 7(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 8(n+5)x^6y^8 + 7(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 8(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$(D_x + D_y)f(x, y) = 6(n+5)x^2y^4 + 10(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 11(n+5)x^4y^7 + 13(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 14(n+5)x^6y^8 + 14(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 15(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$D_y D_x f(x, y) = 8(n+5)x^2y^4 + 21(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 28(n+5)x^4y^7 + 42(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 48(n+5)x^6y^8 + 49(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 56(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$(D_x^2 + D_y^2)f(x, y) = 20(n+5)x^2y^4 + 58(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 65(n+5)x^4y^7 + 85(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 100(n+5)x^6y^8 + 98(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 113(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$D_x^k D_y^k f(x, y) = 8^k(n+5)x^2y^4 + 21^k(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 28^k(n+5)x^4y^7 + 42^k(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 48^k(n+5)x^6y^8 + 49^k(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 56^k(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$D_x D_y (D_x + D_y)f(x, y) = 48(n+5)x^2y^4 + 210(2n+10)x^3y^7 + 308(n+5)x^4y^7 + 546(3n+15)x^6y^7 + 672(n+5)x^6y^8 + 686(2n+10)x^7y^7 + 840(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$S_x S_y f(x, y) = \frac{1}{8}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{1}{21}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{1}{28}(n+5)x^4y^7 + \frac{1}{42}(3n+15)x^6y^7 + \frac{1}{48}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{1}{49}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{1}{56}(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$S_x^k S_y^k f(x, y) = \frac{1}{8^k}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{1}{21^k}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{1}{28^k}(n+5)x^4y^7 + \frac{1}{42^k}(3n+15)x^6y^7 + \frac{1}{48^k}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{1}{49^k}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{1}{56^k}(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$(S_y D_x + S_x D_y)f(x, y) = \frac{20}{8}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{1}{58}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{65}{28}(n+5)x^4y^7 + \frac{85}{42}(3n+15)x^6y^7 + \frac{100}{48}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{98}{49}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{113}{56}(2n+10)x^7y^8,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2S_x Jf(x, y) &= \frac{2}{6}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{2}{10}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{2}{11}(n+5)x^4y^7 + \frac{2}{13}(3n+15)x^6y^7 \\
&+ \frac{2}{14}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{2}{14}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{2}{15}(2n+10)x^7y^8, \\
S_x J D_x D_y f(x, y) &= \frac{8}{6}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{21}{10}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{28}{11}(n+5)x^4y^7 + \frac{42}{13}(3n+15)x^6y^7 \\
&+ \frac{48}{14}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{49}{14}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{56}{15}(2n+10)x^7y^8, \\
S_x^3 Q_{-2} J D_x^3 D_y^3 f(x, y) &= \frac{512}{64}(n+5)x^2y^4 + \frac{9261}{512}(2n+10)x^3y^7 + \frac{21952}{729}(n+5)x^4y^7 \\
&+ \frac{74088}{1331}(3n+15)x^6y^7 + \frac{110592}{1728}(n+5)x^6y^8 + \frac{117649}{1728}(2n+10)x^7y^7 + \frac{175616}{2197}(2n+10)x^7y^8,
\end{aligned}$$

Using the above results in Table 3.1, we obtain

$$NM_1(G) = (D_x + D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 148n + 740,$$

$$NM_2(G) = (D_x D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 462n + 2310,$$

$${}^m NM_2(G) = (S_x S_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 0.425n + 2.124,$$

$$ND_3(G) = D_x D_y (D_x + D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 6138n + 30690,$$

$$NF(G) = (D_x^2 + D_y^2)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 978n + 4890,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
NR_k(G) &= (D_x^k D_y^k)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 8^k(n+5) + 21^k(2n+10) + 28^k(n+5) + 42^k(3n+15) \\
&+ 48^k(n+5) + 49^k(2n+10)x^7 + 56^k(2n+10)x^7,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
NRR_\beta(G) &= (S_x^\beta S_y^\beta)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = \frac{1}{8^k}(n+5) + \frac{1}{21^k}(2n+10) + \frac{1}{28^k}(n+5) + \frac{1}{42^k}(3n+15) \\
&+ \frac{1}{48^k}(n+5) + \frac{1}{49^k}(2n+10) + \frac{1}{56^k}(2n+10),
\end{aligned}$$

$$ND_5(G) = (D_x S_y + S_x D_y)f(x, y)|_{x=1=y} = 26.536n + 132.679,$$

$$NH(G) = 2S_x Jf(x, y)|_{x=1} = 2.072n + 10.36,$$

$$NI(G) = S_x J D_x D_y f(x, y)|_{x=1} = 35.666n + 178.332,$$

$$S(G) = S_x^3 Q_{-2} J D_x^3 D_y^3 f(x, y)|_{x=1} = 601.317n + 3006.585.$$

3.6 Numerical and graphical comparison of indices

In this section, the study on cyclodextrin for various degree-based and its neighborhood degree-based topological indices are compared numerically (Table 3.4, Table 3.5) and graphically (Figure 3.4). To check the variation of indices, different values of n are considered.

By substituting $n = 1$, the values of α -cyclodextrin are determined. Similarly, for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ gives rise to β and γ versions of cyclodextrin derivatives.

It is noticed from Table 3.4 and Table 3.5, that the values of topological indices increase as the n value increases.

Table 3.4: Representation of numerical values of CDs for computed indices.

CDs	n	M_1	M_2	${}^m M_2$	$ReZG_3$	F	R	RR	SDD	H	I	A
$\alpha - CD$	1	360	444	14.666	2376	972	31.42	174.77	168	30	85	301.875
$\beta - CD$	2	420	518	17.11	2772	1134	36.653	203.89	196	35	99.167	702.188
$\gamma - CD$	3	480	592	19.554	3168	1296	41.889	233.02	224	40	113.334	802.500

Table 3.5: Representation of numerical values of CDs for computed indices.

CDs	n	NM_1	NM_2	${}^m NM_2$	ND_3	NF	NR	NRR	ND_5	NH	NI	S
$\alpha - CD$	1	888	2772	2.549	36828	5868	12.834	435.738	159.215	12.432	213.998	3607.902
$\beta - CD$	2	1036	3234	2.974	42966	6846	14.973	508.361	185.751	14.504	249.664	4209.219
$\gamma - CD$	3	1184	3696	3.399	49104	7824	17.112	580.984	212.287	16.576	285.33	4810.536

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Graphical comparison of CDs for computed (a) Degree-based indices (b) Neighborhood degree-based indices.

Conclusion

Cyclodextrins augments the aqueous solubility of drugs that are poorly soluble. They play a major role as excipients in the drug making. CDs are not only used in drugs but also as a food additive and in toiletry commodities. It has been proved that, the characteristics of biomolecules could be reduced or enhanced using cyclodextrins (CDs). We can predispose whether CDs can augment or deter the

effect of the drug by their physicochemical properties. CDs and its derivatives in the form of aero gels are a good alternative in removing contaminants in water. They are used to remove contaminants and toxins from cereals and its products, grape wine, tomato products and beer. The natural objectives for CD complexation are essential oils to retain and enhance its properties of fragrances. The complexes of α, β, γ -CDs are prepared using menthol and polystyrene. In the present work, various degree and neighborhood degree based topological indices are computed using M-polynomial and NM-polynomial respectively for cyclodextrins such as α, β & γ variants. A 3D plot of M-polynomial and NM-polynomial for cyclodextrins are made as shown in the Figures 3.2 & 3.3. It is concluded by the numerical & graphical comparisons of the TIs for all the three derivatives of cyclodextrins. It is observed from the tables of degree-based and neighborhood degree-based indices that as n increases, the indices values also increases.

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Variation of Adriatic and Wiener indices for different cycle lengths and paths

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Abstract

The outcome of a transformation of chemical structure into mathematical model results in numerical descriptor. The chemical compound of a molecule is encoded into a useful number called molecular descriptor. These numerical descriptors have significant importance in the applications of physico-chemical properties of QSAR/QSPR/QSTR studies. Motivated by the work of Vukicevic, Wiener index and Adriatic index are determined for a path attached to cycles of length ≥ 3 . The attached cycle is gradually moved through the set of vertices of the path to study the variation of the Wiener index. It is found that the Adriatic index is equal for all such graphs but the Wiener index, however, appears to be different in every case and lengths.

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Chapter 4

Conclusion and Scope for Future Work

The presented work has focused on gaur gum and its derivatives and also on breast cancer drugs. The molecular structures are considered for study for which the topological indices are determined. Also, the correlation coefficient of these drugs is found with the physical and chemical properties.

Similar work can be considered for different ailments like diabetes, heart disease and so on for which the QSPR analysis can be carried out for the drugs considered.

This work presented a discussion on various chemical compounds in which various degree-based topological indices and their analysis are carried out. Similar work on different chemical compounds for the distance-based topological indices can be carried out by the researchers.

The work can be extended to other concepts like graph operators such as double graphs and subdivision operators. Also, looked into expanding the same concepts for complement of graphs and make an analysis of both the results.

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LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

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